

PHYSICS AND ASTRONOMY TEACHING METHODOLOGY

Matkurbanova Gulchexra

Republic of Karakalpakstan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15688314>

Abstract. *This article discusses innovative technologies in the teaching methodology of physics and astronomy.*

Keywords: *physics and astronomy, error concepts, motion research.*

Modern trends in the modernization of education, which are aimed at increasing the role of teaching and production practice and reducing the number of classes in basic academic disciplines (including physics), encourage the teacher to look for new methods and techniques for systematizing and structuring the material being studied. At the same time, it should be borne in mind that only 61% of all hours allocated for studying a subject fall on classroom lessons, the rest is the student's independent work.

Therefore, today much attention is paid to the introduction of new pedagogical technologies, such as block-modular teaching, distance learning, etc., which allow us to make the educational process differentiated, flexible, problem-oriented, active and creative.

One of the technologies that allows us to better structure and systematize the material being studied is the technology of block-modular teaching. An important advantage of this technology is a multi-level differentiated approach to learning. The main goal of modern higher education is to ensure the self-development of the individual, self-determination, self-realization. An important task facing higher education in general, and physics and astronomy in particular, is the need to adapt the goals, content and methods of education to the requirements of a market economy and the dynamics of socio-economic changes in society. The priority task in this regard is to form in the trainee the qualities required in the modern world: social and professional mobility, the ability and readiness for continuous education and self-study, the ability to work in a team [1].

Another problem of teaching physics and astronomy is that the formal performance of laboratory work by students is reduced to repeating the operations shown by the teacher or described in the instructions, which does not provide the level of training required by educational standards. The use of modern pedagogical technologies helps to solve these and a number of other tasks.

- Substantiation of the need and possibilities of using modern educational technologies in teaching physics and astronomy at a technical university;
- Coordination of the didactic capabilities of modern educational technologies and the regulatory requirements for organizing the educational process at the university;
- Creation of a didactic support of modern educational technologies in teaching physics and astronomy to students of technical universities;
- Experimental verification of the effectiveness of using modern educational technologies in teaching physics and astronomy to students of higher education institutions;

Analyzing all the above definitions, pedagogical technology can be considered as a sustainable educational system based on a certain scientific concept, programming pedagogical

interaction in a certain way, creating conditions for the development of participants in the pedagogical process and assuming a certain, pre-planned education.

In the process of implementing integrated technology, students develop skills in rational organization of their work, skills in working in a group, etc. Didactic support for integrated technology includes:

- curricula;
- teaching aids for lectures on physics and astronomy;
- real visual aids;
- didactic diagnostic materials.

In the implementation of integrated technology, lecture aids play a leading role. They are assigned two functional tasks: teaching the basics of physics and developing the student's personality. To solve these problems, it is proposed to provide students with a ready-made synopsis of the main theoretical material, which can be supplemented with all the necessary explanations and comments during the lecture, containing practical questions and tasks, the implementation of which ensures comprehension. This technology implies the complete independent (or with a certain dose of assistance) achievement of specific goals of educational and cognitive activity by students in the process of working with the module [2].

Modules can be divided into three types: theoretical, practical and combined. In teaching physics and astronomy, practical modules implemented in laboratory classes are considered the most effective. Knowledge, skills and competencies are formed in the process of students' own activities. Students can independently choose both the speed and level of mastering the module. In the process of working on the module, not only a certain dose of physical knowledge is mastered, but also certain personality traits are formed: independent work, rational organization of one's own work, etc.

The last educational element of any modular program is the final control, which serves to verify whether the student has achieved the set didactic goal. Both test tasks and control questions can act in this. The use of modular programs allows you to move from the formal repetition of actions shown by the teacher or described in the instructions to the conscious performance of laboratory work and, as a result, to a high level of mastery of the material being studied.

References

1. Ta'lim to'g'risida: Belarus Respublikasining 2002 yil 25 martdagi qonuni // Belarus Respublikasining normativ-huquqiy hujjatlari milliy reestri. - 2002. - 2/844.
2. Juk, Belarus Respublikasida ta'lim sohasidagi davlat siyosatining ustuvor yo'nalishlari tizimida AI Sifat [Elektron resurs] / AI Juk. - Kirish rejimi: <http://www.grsu.by/cforum/index.php?topic=82.0>. - Kirish sanasi: 01.11.2009.
3. Selevko, G. K. Ta'lim texnologiyalari entsiklopediyasi: 2 jildda / G. K. Selevko. - M. : Maktab texnologiyalari ilmiy-tadqiqot instituti, 2006. - T. 1. - 816 b.